

MIGNEX Policy Dataset

This metadata sheet describes the MIGNEX Policy Dataset, which compiles information on migration-relevant policies in the ten countries covered by the project.

Data type	Policy coding
Unit of analysis	Country
Geographical coverage	10 countries in Africa, the Middle East and Asia (Cabo Verde, Guinea, Ghana, Nigeria, Ethiopia, Somalia, Tunisia, Turkey, Afghanistan, and Pakistan)
Timespan	Data collected between February 2020 and September 2022
Sample size	N/A
Population	N/A
Data origin	Document review (desk research) and interviews with key stakeholders
Thematic coverage	Immigration; Emigration; Transit migration
Data file(s)	mignex-policy-dataset-v1.xlsx
Dataset citation	Please cite as displayed on the Zenodo page for this record.
Detailed documentation	Godin M. and Vargas-Silva C. (2020) Country-level policy review, MIGNEX Handbook Chapter 9 (v1). Oslo: Peace Research Institute Oslo. Available at www.mignex.org/d051 . Godin, M., Vargas-Silva, C. (2022) Documentation of policy review, MIGNEX Handbook Chapter 12 (v1). Oslo: Peace Research Institute Oslo. Available at www.mignex.org/d052 . See also zenodo.org/communities/mignex for additional data and documentation and mignex.org for project information and publications.
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